

FINE ARTS IS A SCIENCE THAT DEVELOPS STUDENTS' ARTISTIC AND CREATIVE ABILITIES

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Abstract: In the current conditions, where the scope of knowledge necessary for a person is gradually expanding, it cannot be limited to mastering the body of certain facts. Therefore, pupils should be taught to independently supplement and enrich their knowledge, to pay attention to the most important scientific and political information. This task provides for the expansion and development of fine arts lessons of students in close connection with the educational process.

Key words: general, secondary education, school, efficiency, unique, talent, effective, research, recommendations, special, psychological and pedagogical, tests, talent.

The main purpose of visual arts is to help primary school students see and feel existence, beauty in nature, distinguish colors, have spatial imagination, develop memory and develop powers of observation. Correctly understand the goal. interpreting the works of the poet and encouraging students to grow spiritually while developing their artistic and creative abilities.

The specifics of fine arts classes in primary school, primarily the content of education, are determined by the age characteristics and psychology of children of primary school age, interests, existing knowledge and skills. It is known that children's passion for visual arts, especially drawing, begins very early. From pedagogy it is known that it begins at 2-3 years. It is interesting to note that children enjoy drawing more than reading and writing. Another characteristic aspect of the visual activity of younger schoolchildren is the desire to simplify drawings. They depict some things from the front, some from the side, and others from above. They bring ease and comfort to children's drawing. Also, children of this age do not describe objects due to chiaroscuro, reduced perspective, and lack of understanding of the rules. There is another feature of children's creativity, which is that the images are not depicted as blocking each other. Because children always perceive things as a whole. These features of the mentioned visual activity are associated with the fact that children's thinking is clear, imaginative and emotional.

Now let's talk about the features of the methodology for conducting fine arts classes in primary school. Mandatory minimum requirements for the content of fine arts education are established in the state educational standard in the following four areas:

1. Perception of existence and art
2. Artistic construction
3. Description by nature
4. Composition activity

According to state educational standards, students completing the fourth grade of primary education should directly know the following:

- tools and materials used in fine arts classes: album, pencil, brush, paints, palette, gouache, watercolor;
- names of colors;
- rules for proper handling of teaching aids used in fine arts classes;
- names and surnames of 15 creative artists and sculptors and the titles of their works;
- primary and secondary colors, chromatic and achromatic colors, warm and cold colors; - types of patterns - arc pattern, square pattern, square pattern, circular pattern;
- names of flowers used in practical art - leaf, se barg, aigul, almond, shobarg, cotton flower;
- terms used in fine and applied arts - artist, color, design, shape, appliqué, rhythm, symmetry, asymmetry, pattern, format.

In the modern educational process, it is better to use modern pedagogical technologies in order to develop the science of fine arts, disseminate it more widely, and improve students' literacy. Pedagogical technology of fine arts is a pedagogical process that can guarantee the achievement of a predetermined goal and the completion of this task, based on the means of instilling artistic knowledge and skills in students in a certain period and in the conditions of a fine arts teacher. When teaching fine arts at school, such forms of pedagogical technology as lesson technology, teaching technology and educational technology are used.

1. Lesson technology is a pedagogical process that guarantees the fulfillment of general pedagogical requirements (didactic and methodological) for the construction, structure and organization of a fine arts lesson lasting 40-45 minutes. That is, fine art is a classroom-lesson system of pedagogical science, which includes the transfer of new knowledge, consolidation of existing

knowledge and competencies, a mixed lesson, testing the competence of knowledge and control lessons. Each of them uses its own technologies.

2. Teaching technology – this technology is a didactic process and a special methodology for teaching and mastering a specific academic subject. Accordingly, teaching technology differs among the five types of fine arts lessons. Because didactics and teaching methods in fine arts classes change, the goals and objectives of classes change, and the technology of its teaching also changes.

3. Information technology is expressed in the content of providing information to students, as well as in the process of instilling in students knowledge and skills in the subject of fine arts, scientific communication, relationships, creative communication between teacher and student, expressed in teaching. content of cooperation processes. That is, it is expressed in a complex of teaching aids, teaching didactics, methods and techniques that can guarantee the ability to transfer to students the knowledge and skills of the theory of art and painting (image) given to students. Because during the lesson, the art teacher gives students the easiest, most concise and scientifically based information about the content of the lesson, tasks and ways to complete them.

The main thing in the technology of teaching fine arts at school is the possibilities, conditions, means, methods and techniques of guaranteed results, and their organization is included in the main task of didactics of teaching fine arts and its principles. Because the didactics of teaching fine arts at school provides, first of all, the scientific basis of the knowledge and skills imparted in each lesson.

The scientific principle ensures that every information provided to students about nature, objects, objects, events or works of art analyzed is based on scientific and scientific knowledge.

Fine art, due to its unique nature, is a subject that cannot be taught without an exhibition. In art classes at school:

- methods of oral presentation, such as conversation, story, question-answer, lecture;
- Demonstration of a visual teaching method, working with illustrations and reproductions, drawing on the board and excursions;
- The method of practical work uses techniques such as painting, modeling, artistic and practical art, compositional work, analysis of works of art, essays on works of art, abstract writing.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the main task of the teacher is to be able to use didactics and teaching methods of a given subject at an excellent level to achieve a given goal.

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